

Towards Dynamic Human-Robot Role Allocation based on Human Ergonomics Assessment

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Abstract—Even though collaborative robots could bring several advantages in industrial environments, still they do not populate adequately logistic and production processes. To enhance their adaptability to fast changes of product demand and, at the same time, ensure the safety of the human operator during the cooperation with cobots, we propose a strategy that can optimally regulate the effort distribution among the involved workers at the planning level during the performance of an assembly task. Such a method allocates an action to a worker only if such actions can be executed with low ergonomic risk, considering also the history of actions executed by the human. The allocation algorithm exploits a physical state estimation of the human operator based on kinematic measurements, which are updated during the cooperative task. To describe the action structure, we used an adapted version of AND/OR Graphs to handle also the role allocation problem. The preliminary experimental results show that the allocation changes during the cooperation, by assigning unsafe actions for the human worker to the robot.

Index Terms—Role Allocation, Ergonomics, Human-Robot Co-operation

I. INTRODUCTION

Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC) envisions humans not only sharing the environment without fences with robots but also partnering with them, to jointly achieve the same tasks. Collaborative robots (cobots) are convenient especially in scenarios of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), characterized by flexible and agile manufacturing requirements, since, compared to highly specialized platforms, they are quickly re-configurable and adaptable to new product demands. Moreover, cobots endurance and precision can be paired to human workers' capabilities of monitoring the task and evaluate different situations. Nevertheless, the teamed performance can be optimized only if each action within the cooperation is allocated to each worker according to their physical status and characteristics: an appropriate design of the collaboration strategy, that includes ergonomics principles, have the potential to clear human operators from hazardous tasks, which would affect the entire process in terms of execution time and expenses.

To implement such principles, we designed a method for human-robot collaborative tasks that dynamically allocates the role to the most suitable worker according to the human

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Fig. 1. Experimental setup. The method not only optimizes the sequence of actions of the assembly, but also the allocation of each single action to the member of the team, by minimizing the ergonomic risk associated with the task.

kinematic state and task features, to achieve a fruitful and ergonomic collaboration.

A commonly used approach for representing industrial assemblies exploits *AND/OR Graphs* (AOGs). AOGs model all the possible assembly sequences of an assembly task. The advantage of using such graphs consists in a compact representation with fewer nodes compared to the general *Directed Graphs* [1]. Recently, the formulation of AOGs has been extended to embed also the role allocation problem in human-robot assembly tasks. *Johannsmeier et Haddadin*, for example, solve the role allocation problem through an A* search on the AOG exploiting the arc-related costs, which account for the agents dissimilarities [2]. To evaluate the task-worker suitability, *Lamon et al.* propose different metrics in terms of agents characteristics, both kinematics and dynamics [3]. The main limitation of these approaches consists in the fact that the optimization runs offline and, hence, the allocated tasks do not change over time according to the human physical status. Moreover, it is important also to consider the online changes of the plan due to the worker's compliance in executing the designated action. The solution proposed by *Darvish et al.* pre-calculates, first, all the assembly sequences offline. Successively, during task execution, the human worker can execute the allocated action or delegate it to the cobot. In the latter case, the AOG automatically switches to a new branch [4]. However, the actions are all allocated beforehand; then the result of the allocation remains fixed for the whole teamwork.

Fig. 2. Framework scheme. At each iteration, the algorithm returns the next task and the allocated worker. After the execution of the task by the human, the joint-level ergonomic risk and, hence, the kinematic wear value $\mathbf{V}(t)$, that contains the kinematic history of the joint, are evaluated. According to that, the AOG hyper-arcs cost are updated for next allocation.

II. METHODS

An AOG is a graph described by a set of nodes $N = \{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_{|N|}\}$ and a set of hyper-arcs $H = \{h_1, h_2, \dots, h_{|H|}\}$. Each node $n \in N$ represents a state of the decomposed task, while hyper-arcs define the transitions between states. Each $h \in H$ describes a two-to-one transition, meaning that it connects a father node with two child nodes.

The child nodes linked with by the same h are in a logical AND, while different hyper-arcs with the same parent node are in logical OR. Moreover, it is possible to associate a cost to hyper-arcs, $c_{h_1}, c_{h_2}, \dots, c_{h_{|H|}}$. The only node without a father is named root, while the nodes without children are leaf nodes.

While the AOG, by itself, models the assembly task, the formalization of the role allocation problem with an AOG requires two additional sets, representing the workers involved in the collaboration, $W = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{|W|}\}$ and the assembly actions, $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{|A|}\}$ that workers have to perform. To model the fact that each action can be performed by all the workers, the same nodes that represent an assembly are connected by $|W|$ hyper-arcs. In this way, it is possible to assign to each hyper-arc a cost that represents the suitability of a worker to that action.

The assembly sequence and the agent allocated to each action are successively calculated through a custom AO* search. The algorithm inspects the graph from the root, the state where all the pieces are assembled, to the leaf nodes, with the constraint to inspect all the leaves, as they represent the atomic pieces, using the sum of the costs of the traveled hyper-arcs as a heuristic. By minimizing the heuristic it is possible to retrieve the desired path. Since costs change during the task execution, the search is called repetitively after the completion of each action on a reduced graph from the root node to the last reached state.

This feature, which allows to online compute the solution with variable costs, is suitable for the proposed method. (see Figure 2). For simplicity, the costs for the actions of robot w_r are fixed, $c_{h_j, w_r} = \bar{c}_{medium}$. Instead, costs for human actions are computed according to a joint-level estimation of the ergonomic risk associated with the execution of an

action by a human worker. In particular, to avoid the human worker stands for a long time in risky postures, we monitor the *kinematic wear* $V(t)$ of each joint, which represents the history of its usage. This value should identify how long each joint stayed in unhealthy configurations. After the execution of each action by a human worker, the kinematic wear vector $\mathbf{V}(t) = [V_1(t) \dots V_m(t)]^T$ is computed, where m is the size of the monitored joints. Each action is described by a constant weights vector α that encodes the level of involvement of each joint during the action performance. The prediction of the risk associated with the execution of the next action a_{k+1} , given $\mathbf{V}(t_k)$, where t_k is the instant when a_k was completed, and α_{k+1} , is computed as:

$$\beta_{k+1} = \alpha_{k+1}^T \mathbf{V}(t_k) = \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_{k+1,i} V_i(t_k) \quad (1)$$

If β_{k+1} is greater than a certain threshold β_{th} then a_{k+1} is considered damageable for the human worker and, hence, a large cost \bar{c}_{high} is assigned to the hyper-arc that models it. Otherwise, a small cost \bar{c}_{low} is assigned:

$$c_{h_j, w_h} = \begin{cases} \bar{c}_{high} & \text{if } \beta_{k+1} \geq \beta_{th}, \\ \bar{c}_{low} & \text{if } \beta_{k+1} < \beta_{th}. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $\bar{c}_{high} > \bar{c}_{medium} > \bar{c}_{low}$. These computations hold for all the actions executable by the human after t_k .

III. EXPERIMENTS

To evaluate the method we defined a simple assembly task that consists of a sub-assembly of a small table by joining a corner joint CJ with three aluminum profiles, which are two sides S_1, S_2 and a leg L of such a table. The profiles S_2 and L have the same length, while S_1 is shorter. Each profile should be assembled with the corner joint, either by a human worker or by a Franka Emika Panda cobot. The defined actions of the task are: (a_1) pick and assemble CJ with S_1 , (a_2) pick and assemble S_2 with the sub-assembly CJ_S_1 , (a_3) pick and assemble L with the sub-assembly $CJ_S_1_S_2$. A motion capture system is in charge of capturing the human kinematic configuration that is used by the

ergonomics assessment method. In our experiments, an IMUs-based suit, Xsens (xsens.com), was used for the user readiness and unlimited field of view of the system. Nevertheless, other motion capture systems could be employed, such as infrared or RGB-D camera systems running skeleton tracking algorithms. In particular, the latter looks promising since it does not require the worker to wear any sensorized suit or marker. In this experiment, we exploited Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) [5]. A score that represents the postural risk is associated with each joint (shoulder, elbow, wrist, trunk and neck): the higher the score, the higher the risk. In Figure 1 the experimental setup is presented.

To model the *kinematic wear* index at the joint level we chose an RC circuit behavior:

$$V_i(t) = 1 - (1 - V_i(t_k)) e^{-\int_0^t \frac{G_i(\tau)}{C_i} d\tau} \quad (3)$$

where $V_i(t)$, C_i and $G_i(t)$ are the *kinematic wear* level, the endurance capacity in the most hazardous configuration and the current RULA score of the i -th upper body joint, respectively. The i -th joint motion during the task execution generates a change of the RULA score $G_i(t)$, which, in turn, increases the corresponding kinematic wear $V_i(t)$, with a slope proportional to the risk level of the new posture.

The three aluminum profiles are placed in front of the human worker, but on the opposite side of the table (see Figure 1). For this reason, the actions require mainly the worker to bend the trunk, and, hence, such joint is the most stressed joint at the end of the task. Therefore, for simplicity, $\alpha = [0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0]^T$, that means that in the computation of β_{k+1} , only the kinematic wear of the trunk joint is evaluated. The accumulated effort from previous tasks of the human worker cause the kinematic wear to start from non-zero initial conditions, $V_{trunk}(0) = 0.7$. The cost of hyper-arcs modeling robot actions is fixed to $\bar{c}_{medium} = 5$. The high and low cost values associated with the human actions are $\bar{c}_{high} = 10$ and $\bar{c}_{low} = 1$, respectively. The value of β_{th} is set experimentally to 0.8. The offline allocation would assign all the three actions to the human, since $\beta_{k+1} = \alpha_{k+1}^T \mathbf{V}(0)$ with $k = 0, 1, 2$ is under threshold $\beta_{th} = 0.8$. In the online role allocation, instead, the values of $\mathbf{V}(t)$ used for the computation of β_{k+1} are updated after the execution of each action, and, therefore, the algorithm acknowledges a risk in using the trunk for the three consecutive actions and allocates the last one to the robot (see Figure 3).

IV. CONCLUSION

The proposed allocation strategy, exploiting AOG properties, can handle the effort distribution among the workers involved in the cooperation. The hyper-arcs cost, modeling the history of the human worker's joints wear, are updated during the whole duration of the task. It is important to highlight that the algorithm would assign the future actions that involve the overstressed joints to the robot, while the human would be still eligible to execute actions that do not involve such joints. In this way, the optimal search algorithm guarantees to assign

Fig. 3. Experimental results. (Top) The trunk *kinematic wear* increasing behavior across the execution of actions a_1 , a_2 , a_3 , starting from $V_{trunk}(0) = 0.7$ (here $\beta_{k+1} = V_{trunk}(t_k)$ with $k = 0, 1, 2$). In red the β_{th} value experimentally set to 0.8. (Mid) Comparison between the role allocation output in offline and online mode. (Bottom) Snapshots of the three assembly actions executed by the human (the first two) and by the robot (the third one).

actions addressing human ergonomics, as the first step towards an ergonomics-based role allocation.

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